

ANALYSIS OF THEORETICAL AND SCIENTIFIC APPROACHES TO INCLUSIVE EDUCATION SYSTEMS AROUND THE WORLD

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Abstract. *This study aims to use new programs in the use of educational methods based on psychological methods used to eliminate mental and intellectual problems in children with disabilities in the process of inclusive education. During this study, we studied the inclusive education program of psychologists-pedagogues and provided information on the use of methods based on inclusive education with examples.*

Keywords: *Inclusive education, psychological research, psychological education, integrated education, discrimination, pedagogical research.*

DUNYO BO'YICHA INKLYUZIV TA'LIM SISTEMASINING NAZARIY VA ILMIY YONDASHUVLAR TAHLILI

Annotatsiya. *Ushbu tadqiqot inklyuziv ta'lim jarayonida nogironligi mavjud bo'lgan bolalarda ruhiy va aqliy muammolarini bartaraf etishda qo'llaniladigan psixologik metodlarga asoslangan ta'lim usullaridan foydalanishda yangi dasturlarni qo'llash maqsadga muvofiqdir. Biz ushbu tadqiqot davomida psixolog-pedagoglarning inklyuziv ta'lim dasturini o'rganib chiqdik va misollar bilan inklyuziv ta'limga asoslangan metodlarni qo'llash bo'yicha ma'lumotlarni keltirib o'tdik.*

Kalit so'zlar: *Inklyuziv ta'lim, psixologik tadqiqotlar, psixologik ta'lim, integratsion ta'lim, diskriminatsiya, pedagogik tadqiqotlar.*

АНАЛИЗ ТЕОРЕТИЧЕСКИХ И НАУЧНЫХ ПОДХОДОВ К СИСТЕМАМ ИНКЛЮЗИВНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ В МИРЕ

Аннотация. *Целью данного исследования является использование новых программ в применении образовательных методов, основанных на психологических методах, используемых для преодоления психических и интеллектуальных проблем у детей с ограниченными возможностями в процессе инклюзивного образования. В ходе данного исследования мы рассмотрели программу инклюзивного образования психологов и педагогов и привели примеры использования методов, основанных на инклюзивном образовании.*

Ключевые слова: Инклюзивное образование, психологические исследования, психологическое образование, интегрированное образование, дискриминация, педагогические исследования.

Introduction

Inclusive education is a pedagogical-psychological collaborative education based on an education system recognized by the entire community as the most humane and effective. Inclusive education is an educational process in which all children, regardless of their physical, mental, intellectual and other problems, receive education together with their peers in a common way, in their own home and territory, in schools where all conditions are created for their needs. The goal of inclusive education is to ensure that children with special needs receive a full-fledged education in general education institutions, based on their capabilities, and to create the necessary conditions for each child in educational institutions. Various forms of education have been organized for children with disabilities. Based on psychological programs, it will be possible to study the theoretical and scientific essence of the inclusive education system by organizing special education, home education, inclusive, and integrated education stages. Special psychological education - specially organized boarding schools, schools, home education - education organized in the family for children who do not have the opportunity to study in educational institutions; inclusive, integrative education - harmonious education organized in general education institutions; houses of mercy - specially organized boarding-type education for children with severe developmental disabilities. The life path of a disabled child who is not involved in inclusive education: stays at home until the age of 7. For 10 or 12 years, when he studies with children like him in a special educational institution (boarding school, school), his communication with healthy people is somewhat limited. After graduating, he will need someone else's help to live effectively among healthy people. At this time, the child will be 19 years old and his parents will be middle-aged or older. If he is not involved in college or other types of education, this person will remain in the care of his family, as most parents try to stay at home to care for him. The reason: they do not have enough confidence in their child to work or enter into other relationships among healthy people. In addition, they are worried that those around them will have a negative attitude towards their child.

As a result, a person with disabilities is doomed to remain in a narrow circle of people. They start a family late. If the spouse is like them, the parents will have to "pull" a small family again. If they have children, the responsibility will increase again. However, during this period, the parents will be much older and they themselves may need the care of others.

Therefore, the parents will live their lives in old age, thinking about the fate of their child. If a child with disabilities is involved in inclusive education early, from childhood in the neighborhood they will play with neighboring children, get to know them, and begin to understand national values.

During preschool education, children learn to communicate with healthy people and peers around them, learn to be independent early, and are ready for school education. In inclusive education, they continue to communicate with healthy people during the period of development, understand the negative and positive views of those around them, and find their own independent position in relation to them. Now he is stepping into an independent life, ready to study, work, and participate in various relationships as an independent citizen. Parents and loved ones are not worried about him going out. Those who know who he is and what he is capable of in society trust him. As a result, he will be able to start a family and provide for his family. However, to this day, there are many problems in implementing them in life. In some countries, when laws or decisions are adopted on general education, the issue of education of children with disabilities is not included. However, recognizing inclusive education does not depend only on the adoption of laws. Combating discrimination (separating people) and social misconceptions is the most important thing. That is, recognizing inclusive education and conducting propaganda and awareness-raising activities among the population is the first priority. The principle of inclusive education being open to all. Over the past two decades, significant progress has been made in the education of children with special needs in the general education system. However, the implementation of inclusive education has been mainly in urban areas, and children with special needs are still excluded from education in rural areas, or parents in rural areas face difficulties in ensuring that their children with disabilities attend special institutions in cities. Therefore, the inclusion of children with special needs in inclusive education should be ensured in all regions, covering all children with special needs. The principle of accessibility. Accessibility is the quality of public buildings, especially the accessibility of schools for children with special needs. A child should not be excluded from a regular school because the stairs are not wheelchair accessible or the school toilet is not wheelchair accessible.

Creating such facilities does not require a lot of money. A new school building should be built from the very beginning, taking into account the needs of children with special needs. Of course, good facilities for children with special needs do not cause any problems for children with normal development. Creating physical connections helps to solve the main problems of inclusive education. The principle of decentralization. The essence of this principle is expressed as follows: Inclusive education services should be an integrated part of the general education system.

The tasks of the inclusive education system should be decentralized to place responsibility and management on local education authorities, and the opportunities should be adapted to local conditions. Decentralization is important for achieving optimal integration. This is especially true in rural settings. The tasks of inclusive education are to keep children with special needs with their parents, to allow them to receive education in schools close to them, just like their peers. This is important for the formation of personal qualities in them. Disruption of the normal development of a child with special needs can lead to conditions that are even more serious than disability. The principle of a comprehensive approach to inclusive education can be considered theoretically, based on psychological foundations. It is necessary to approach children with special needs not only as disabled, but also as a whole. This requires planning for children with special needs, taking into account their possible needs throughout their lives. In our country, legal norms have been developed for organizing inclusive education based on the social needs and personal interests of learners, ensuring a strong integration of science, education and production. Important tasks have been set, such as “strengthening the material and technical base of educational institutions in order to organize inclusive education for children with special educational needs, adapting curricula, increasing the capacity for quality health-improving educational services, and training highly qualified personnel suitable for this process.” Improving the quality of education in primary education, effectively organizing a learning environment that is appropriate to the capabilities of students and takes into account the norms of state educational standards, and strengthening the cooperation of organizations and public institutions in this process are becoming increasingly important. Addressing these socio-pedagogical issues requires mutually beneficial cooperation between education, healthcare, and community organizations to provide children with disabilities with quality educational services.

This requires the clarification of methodological skills of primary school teachers, cluster approaches to the development of professional competence, organizational factors, pedagogical and psychological conditions, didactic requirements for organizing classes in inclusive classes. In many countries, a system of using methodologies based on inclusive education has been introduced, and this method is recognized as an effective method of helping children with disabilities.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be said that the use of new pedagogical and psychological methods in the development of modern methodologies for inclusive education will contribute to the education, psychological, intellectual, and spiritual development of children with disabilities. We believe that it is appropriate to use pedagogical and psychological methods and educational systems of countries with developed educational programs in the development of these methods.

By using accessible methods of education for children with disabilities, it is possible to form new stages of an effective education system.

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